

D4.2 INITIAL LIST OF COMMON TERMS AND METADATA STANDARDS DECEMBER 2023

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Abstract

AgrifoodTEF, a consortium of European testing and validation infrastructures, is committed to supporting agri-food companies in developing AI and robotics solutions through field development within established facilities. The initiative aims to bridge the gap between research efforts in these areas and the tangible creation of products that support efficient and sustainable agriculture aligned with the stringent usability and economic requirements of end users. By leveraging existing experimental farms and AI/Robotics facilities in representative European regions, AgrifoodTEF consolidates resources to strengthen the European Union's central role in ensuring global food security. This consolidation focuses on testing and validating facilities involving the best experts in AI and robotics technology and relevant stakeholders. The strategic framework includes the creation of standards for dataset development, data sovereignty, algorithm interoperability and benchmarking. GAIA-X's agro-domain ambassadors across Europe play an integral role in this endeavor. Although each TEF node emphasizes independent operations tailored to specific specialties and regional needs, a coherent set of guidelines and standards is shared by all nodes. Mutual service support is a feature of the various regions represented by nodes and satellites.

The overarching goal is to improve Europe's position by stimulating the widespread adoption of advanced Agri-Food solutions. Task 4.1 within this mission focuses on establishing common terms and metadata standards within AgrifoodTEF. This includes standardized data labeling formats, an ontology of terms and the development of data quality labels and AI models. Existing benchmarks such as ISO standards for AI, results of Horizon 2020 projects (e.g. Atlas and Demeter) and AEF standards form the basis for this effort. This task also initiates specialized working groups (e.g., robotics, computer vision, remote sensing) to facilitate implementation and identify gaps in existing standards. This task is closely related to Task 4.2, where standardization needs emerge and are coordinated for the development of new services. Through collaborative efforts, AgrifoodTEF strives to create a harmonized language and robust standards that strengthen the network's capacity for innovation and coherence in Agrifood technology.

Executive summary

This deliverable is an important step in establishing a standardized framework within AgrifoodTEF. It gathers essential terms and metadata standards, in line with the goal of Task 4.1 to create a common language and metadata standards fundamental for the interoperability of the diverse services offered within AgrifoodTEF. This includes standardized data labels, ontologies for efficient communication, and quality labels for data and AI models.

After some background information, providing an overview of standards and organizations that form the backbone of uniform practices and protocols within the agri-food sector, this deliverable introduces the template for the Service Data Management Plan (sDMP). The sDMP template was jointly prepared and then discussed and finalized during a workshop of the project meeting in Osnabrück. To efficiently collect the required information on all services and general partners, nodes and satellites were tasked with completing the sDMP for their respective services.

The sDMP survey revealed common terminologies used in the AgrifoodTEF portfolio of services, and categorized them across diverse dimensions, highlighting critical aspects such as data collection, quality assessment, and metadata management. This summary provides an overarching insight into the core aspects outlined in the sDMPs, serving as a foundational guide for subsequent operational steps within AgrifoodTEF:

- **Data Collection:** Diverse data types are collected through varied methods and tools, highlighting the breadth and contextuality of data collection practices.
- **Data Quality and Use:** Rigorous quality assessments, including AI model testing, standardized for reliability and suitability across services.

The comprehensive explanation of data types, collection practices and quality assessment methods lays the foundation for robust data management and evaluation frameworks within the project. These efforts strengthen uniformity, consistency and integrity in handling data across facets of service delivery, paving the way for future joint developments.

- **Metadata:** Comprehensive metadata management encompassing diverse information, tools, and obligations based on context.
- **Metadata Standards:** Establishment through domain-specific vocabularies, aiming for clarity, understandability, and compliance with FAIR Data principles.

A Metadata analysis is performed to examine the types of metadata that are most prevalent, the tools and platforms used for managing this metadata, and the standards applied to ensure consistency and quality across various services. While revealing insights into organizational practices, it also highlighted gaps due to low service readiness. This emphasizes the need for refined metadata strategies as services mature, ensuring robust data organization and management aligned with evolving needs. Another key observation is the predominant use of traditional folder structures for organizing metadata, indicating a preference for user-friendly approaches but possibly lacking in more sophisticated data management systems. Time stamps and location metadata emerge as fundamental elements, highlighting chronological and geographical contexts in agrifood experiments. However, it may also indicate a lack of knowledge of data management systems that are much more capable of maintaining consistency and integrity of the data.

- **Previous European Projects:** Varied engagement levels with prior projects, indicating differing approaches in leveraging their outcomes.

Engagement in digital agrifood ecosystems through projects like Demeter and IOF2020 hasn't fully translated into strong integration of terminology linked to FAIR Data principles. This signifies a gap between engagement in projects and the adoption of standardized practices within AgrifoodTEF.

- **Data Sharing and Protection:** Emphasis on secure and collaborative data management, ensuring compliance with ethical guidelines and regulations.

Addressing the challenge of secure data sharing and protection is identified as essential. Establishing reliable data management practices to safeguard agricultural data and support collaborative efforts within AgrifoodTEF services remains a critical focus area.

The sDMP survey also highlights the need for a comprehensive ontology to improve data consistency and interoperability. In this early stage, developing and integrating ontologies present both challenges and opportunities for the AgrifoodTEF project. As the project evolves, continuous refinement and adaptation of these ontologies will be indispensable to stay in line with service and customer needs.

While there is a lot of work in implementing consistent, interoperable data management practices, it is essential to balance these efforts. Excessive emphasis on standardization may hinder the final project goal of deploying qualitative services. Data management is essential, yet it must always serve as a means to an end, facilitating improved services for our clients. This is where our working groups play an important role. Their task is to exchange information on existing data ontologies and management tools across various technical domains of AgrifoodTEF, such as robotics, sensor testing, and AI pipelines, to ensure service quality. These groups are key in ensuring that each step towards standardization and a common language is focused on enhancing service delivery.

Overall, this pursuit of a common language and standardised framework within AgrifoodTEF is an ongoing journey, with this deliverable being only the starting point of a robust and dynamic process.

1. Introduction

This deliverable is an essential step towards a coherent and standardized framework within the AgrifoodTEF ecosystem. It focuses on compiling an initial list of common terms and metadata standards, which is fundamental for the various services offered within the AgrifoodTEF landscape, especially considering the project is still in its early stages

This preliminary effort aligns with the primary objective of Task 4.1 to implement a universal language and structured framework, including the development of standardized formats for data labels and a consistent ontology of terms for efficient communication across all services.

Emphasizing the early stage of the project, the deliverable also includes the formulation and implementation of quality labels for both data and AI models within the TEF are an integral part of this effort. Drawing on insights and inspiration from established standards such as ISO standards for AI, findings from important Horizon 2020 and HE projects such as Atlas and Demeter, and AEF standards, this work aims to merge and integrate relevant existing and emerging standards into the AgrifoodTEF framework.

To ensure the effective adoption and use of these standards across the network, specialized working groups have been formed to focus on different topic areas (e.g., robotics, computer vision, remote sensing, etc.). These groups play a key role in evaluating existing standards and identifying potential gaps to refine and improve the standards landscape, closely linked to the standardization needs identified in Task 4.2.

Furthermore, this deliverable functions as a central coordination point for aligning related standards with the development of new services within AgrifoodTEF. By synchronizing emerging services with relevant standards, it aims to ensure coherence, compatibility, and uniformity in the evolving landscape of agrifood innovation.

In essence, this deliverable aims to start the groundwork for a standardized language and framework within the AgrifoodTEF, fostering collaboration, interoperability and innovation across services and initiatives in these early stages of the project.

2. Background

Common terms and metadata standards increase efficient and effective data sharing in the agrifood sector. Common standards can make different organizations confident that they are using the same data definitions and formats. This helps to avoid errors and create new opportunities for data analysis.

In addition, the common standards enable the integration of different data sources into a single system. This can be important for organizations that create added value from the combination of various sources, such as remote sensors, registration or process monitoring tools.

Overall, common terms and metadata standards improve the efficiency, accuracy, and interoperability of data in the agrifood sector. This can lead to better decision-making, improved food security or may assist in developing new data-driven technologies.

Metadata serves as the foundation of digital curation and plays a major role in the accessibility and usability of digital resources. It encompasses descriptive and contextual information linked to another object or resource, typically organized into structured elements. Metadata not only describes the information resource but also aids users in locating and retrieving it while supporting content and access management. Without metadata, a digital resource may become practically impossible to retrieve, identify, or utilize.

Metadata consists of various elements organized according to the specific functions they serve. A metadata standard typically supports multiple defined functions and outlines the elements required to fulfill these functions. These functions may include the following:

- **Descriptive Metadata:** This type of metadata aids users in identifying, locating, and retrieving information resources. It often incorporates controlled vocabularies for classification and indexing and links to related resources.
- **Technical Metadata:** Technical metadata details the processes used to create or the requirements for using a digital object.
- **Administrative Metadata:** Administrative metadata manages various administrative aspects of a digital object, including intellectual property rights, acquisition information, and documentation related to the creation, alteration, and version control of the metadata itself (sometimes referred to as "meta-data").
- **Use Metadata:** Using metadata facilitates user access, tracks user interactions, and manages information related to multiple versions of a resource.
- **Preservation Metadata:** Preservation metadata documents actions taken to preserve a digital resource, such as migration processes and checksum calculations.

Metadata standards typically originate as schemas developed by specific user communities to accurately describe their resource types. This development process involves community consensus and formal processes for submitting, approving, and publishing new elements. Adopted metadata definitions are controlled and guided by the user community. Published specifications are often centralized by consortia, organizations or companies and are made accessible through websites or Metadata Registries. These specifications include semantic definitions of elements and standardized representations in digital formats. Semantic definitions encompass both Metadata Structure Standards, ensuring consistent structure for data sharing, and Metadata Content Standards, ensuring effective machine searches through consistent data entry and using controlled vocabularies like authority files, thesauri, or encoding schemes for access points.

Metadata schemas evolve in response to community needs and can gain widespread acceptance during development. In some scenarios, there is maintenance by nationally or internationally recognized centers, such as the Library of Congress, or support from professional bodies to enhance visibility and adoption within the community.

In addition to metadata standards, the agri-food industry relies on technical and data standards. Technical standards regulate the production, processing, and distribution of agri-food products, ensuring safety, quality, and environmental protection. Data standards define data structure and content, enabling data sharing, analysis, and transparency. The development and implementation of these standards contribute to the efficiency, effectiveness, and transparency of the agri-food sector.

Furthermore, ontologies play a major role in structuring and organizing information, making it understandable and usable by humans and computers. They are integral to the semantic web, revolutionizing internet interactions by structuring information in a machine-readable manner. Ontologies find application in information modeling, data integration, improving search results, and training artificial intelligence systems to understand the world better. They are a powerful tool for enhancing the organization and accessibility of information in various contexts.

2.1. International standardization organizations

Many organizations work with standards in the agriculture sector. Here are a few of the most prominent ones:

- [International Organization for Standardization \(ISO\)](#). ISO is the world's largest developer of standards. It has developed standards that are relevant to the agriculture sector, including ISO 22000 on food safety, ISO 14001 on environmental management, and ISO 50001 on energy management.
- [International Electrotechnical Commission \(IEC\)](#). IEC is the world's leading organization for developing and publishing international standards for all electrical, electronic, and related technologies. It has developed standards that are relevant to the agriculture sector, including IEC 62061 on functional safety of electrical/electronic/programmable electronic safety-related systems.
- [International Plant Protection Convention \(IPPC\)](#). IPPC is an international organization that protects plants from pests and diseases. It has developed several standards that are relevant to the agriculture sector, including ISPM 15 on phytosanitary measures for wood packaging materials.
- [Codex Alimentarius Commission \(CAC\)](#). CAC is a joint FAO/WHO food standards program that develops international standards, codes of practice, guidelines, and other recommendations for food safety. It has developed standards that are relevant to the agriculture sector, including CAC/RCP 1-2020 on general principles of food hygiene.
- [Global Good Agricultural Practices \(GLOBALGAP\)](#). GLOBALGAP is an international certification program that promotes good agricultural practices. It has developed standards that are relevant to the agriculture sector, including GLOBALGAP for fresh produce.

There are many **common terms and metadata standards** used in the agrifood sector. Some of the most widely used standards include:

- **AGROVOC:** This is an agricultural thesaurus that provides a controlled vocabulary for the agrifood sector. It is used to annotate and index agricultural data and information. [AGROVOC: AGROVOC Multilingual Thesaurus \(fao.org\)](https://www.fao.org/agrovoc/)
- **Dublin Core:** This is a set of metadata elements that describe resources, such as websites, documents, and images. It is a widely used standard for metadata in many different sectors, including the agrifood sector. [DCMI: Home \(dublincore.org\)](https://dublincore.org/)
- **FAOSTAT:** This is a database of agricultural statistics maintained by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. It uses the AGROVOC thesaurus and the Dublin Core metadata standard. https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:FAO_logo.svg
- **SAML:** This is an XML-based standard for authentication and authorization. It is used in the agrifood sector to securely share data between different systems. <https://www.sigcorp.com/blog/introduction-to-saml-2-0-single-sign-on/>
- **AgGateway:** is a non-profit organization that develops and promotes open standards for the agrifood sector. AgGateway's mission is to "enable the efficient and effective exchange of data and information in the agrifood sector through the development and promotion of open standards." <https://www.aggateway.org/GetConnected/StandardsGuidelines.aspx>
- **AgroEDI:** This stands for Agricultural Electronic Data Interchange. It is a set of standards for the electronic exchange of data in the agrifood sector. AgroEDI standards are important for the agrifood sector because they help to improve efficiency, transparency, and traceability. AgroEDI has worked strongly on field data exchange by implementing the DAPLOS (Data PLOt Sheet) format. <https://agroedieurope.fr/>
- **The W3C Semantic Web standards:** These standards are used to represent and exchange data in a machine-readable format. They are used in the agrifood sector to facilitate the integration of different data sources. The working group W3C Semantic Web Activity is developing a set of standards for representing and exchanging data on the semantic web. https://www.w3.org/2001/sw/wiki/Main_Page

These are just a few common terms and metadata standards used in the agrifood sector. The specific standards that are used will vary depending on the specific application. In addition to these standards, there are also several emerging standards that are being developed for the agrifood sector. These include:

- **Atlas:** This is a Horizon 2020 project that is developing standards for the interoperability of agrifood data and services. <https://www.atlas-h2020.eu/>
(https://www.eca.europa.eu/Lists/ECADocuments/SR22_16/SR_Big_Data_in_CAP_EN.pdf)
- **Demeter:** This is a Horizon 2020 project that is developing standards for the traceability of agrifood products. <https://h2020-demeter.eu/>
(https://h2020-demeter.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/DEMETER_D21_final.pdf)

These emerging standards are expected to play an increasingly important role in the agrifood sector in the years to come.

2.2. ISO standards

ISO standards for agriculture

ISO standards for agriculture cover the entire agricultural process, from irrigation and GPS to agricultural machinery, animal welfare, and sustainable farm management. They help to promote efficient farming methods while ensuring that all products in the supply chain, from farm to fork, meet adequate safety and quality standards. By providing internationally agreed-upon solutions to global agricultural challenges, ISO standards also promote sustainability and sound environmental management, which contribute to a better future.

More information: <https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/store/en/PUB100412.pdf>

Some examples:

- **ISO 12934:** This standard specifies terminology for agricultural field equipment. This provides terms and definitions for agricultural field equipment designed primarily for use in agricultural operations to produce food and fibre.
- **ISO 17989-1:** This standard gives manufacturers of tractors and agricultural machinery the guidance they need to integrate sustainability principles into the whole life cycle of their products. The standard applies specifically to equipment used to produce food, fibers, fuel, and lumber for humans and livestock.
- **ISO 18497:** Agricultural machinery and tractors - Safety of highly automated agricultural machines, principles for design.
- **ISO 20966:** Automatic milking installations – Requirements and testing
- **ISO 4002:** Equipment for sowing and planting
- **ISO 26262:** an international standard specifying requirements for functional safety of electrical/electronic (E/E) systems in road vehicles. It applies to all road vehicles, including passenger cars, trucks, buses, and motorcycles. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_26262
- **ISO 25119:** an international standard specifying requirements for the functional safety of electrical/electronic (E/E) systems in agricultural and forestry machinery. It applies to all agricultural and forestry machinery, including tractors, harvesters, and balers.

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42: Standardization in the area of Artificial Intelligence

Serve as the focus and proponent for JTC 1's standardization program on Artificial Intelligence. Provide guidance to JTC 1, IEC, and ISO committees developing Artificial Intelligence applications

<https://www.iso.org/search.html?q=ISO/IEC%20JTC%201/SC%2042>

- **ISO/IEC TR 29119-11:** Software and systems engineering — Software testing. Guidelines on the testing of AI-based systems. It can help organizations to ensure that their AI/ML software is safe, reliable, and meets the needs of their users. <https://www.iso.org/standard/79016.html>

ISO/TC 211: Geographic information/Geomatics

Standardization in the field of digital geographic information. This work aims to establish a structured set of standards for information concerning objects or phenomena that are directly or indirectly associated with a location relative to the Earth. Within the scope of geographic information, these standards may specify methods, tools, and services for data management. Data management is understood to include acquiring, processing, analyzing, accessing, presenting, and publishing data for users and systems.

- **ISO 19115:** This is an international standard that defines a metadata schema for geographic information. It is used to describe geographic datasets, such as maps and satellite images. <https://www.fgdc.gov/metadata/iso-suite-of-geospatial-metadata-standards>
- **ISO 15926:** This is an international standard that defines a metadata schema for agricultural and biological data. It is used to describe agricultural datasets, such as crop yields and livestock populations. <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-9717/10/10/2155>

3. Common terms

3.1. Service Data Management Plan Survey

Collecting the necessary information across all satellites and nodes, covering all services, is a challenging task, especially in the early stages of the project when many services are under development or in an immature stage. The Service Data Management Plan (sDMP) was developed iteratively. Initially, the partners involved in task 4.1 drafted the first version. Then this document was discussed in detail at a WP2 workshop on September 19, 2023 in Osnabrück. All received comments and improvement suggestions were carefully integrated, leading to the final version approved by the consortium, as described in Annex 1.

In the next phase, nodes and satellites were tasked with completing the sDMP for their respective services to establish common terminology and understand metadata standards within the AgrifoodTEF service portfolio. Six nodes/satellites completed the data management plan survey, while Germany and Poland, which have no current services in the catalog, did not participate. For 59 of the 175 services sDMP was completed. Other services were in too early stages of deployment, to complete the sDMP or had an established sDMP that was also applicable. This section overviews the current common terms maintained among the AgrifoodTEF partners.

The result of these efforts is a collection of common terms. Two important steps in data management are data collection and quality assessment. Sections “3.2 Common terms in data collection” and “3.3 Common terms in data quality assessment” give an overview of the terms that occurred in the sDMPs and provide an essential reference framework for further operational steps within AgrifoodTEF.

3.2. Common terms in data collection

Data Types and Categories:

- **Agricultural Data:** E.g., plant discrimination, crop mapping, environmental characteristics
- **User Feedback & Acceptance:** contact information and user feedback
- **Raw Data:** Raw Sensor outputs, e.g., images (Soil, Crop, Spray pattern), GPS position and orientation, textual sensor outputs
- **System-Specific Data:** Specifics to system functionalities and efficiency, e.g., power consumption, energy loss, communication load, health monitoring logs
- **Data for AI-Based Systems:** AI systems' input data, e.g., video, images, sensor acquisitions, path planning, spatial orientation
- **AI description and Documentation:** Ability to understand the AI design, e.g., model weight, system documentation

Data formats:

- **CSV (Comma-Separated Values):** Used for tabular or textual data across multiple instances.
- **Image Formats (PNG, JPG, TIFF):** Used for images and image-related data in various applications.
- **Textual Formats (TXT, DOCX, XLSX):** Used for textual documentation and data storage.
- **Binary Data:** Used for device-specific or unspecified binary data.
- **YOLO or COCO labels:** Both YOLO and COCO are widely used in computer vision research and serve as essential benchmarks for assessing the performance of object detection algorithms and models.
- **Task-Specific Labels:** Labels designed for particular services, projects or tasks

Data collection locations:

- **In the Field:** Many instances involve field collection, whether for agricultural studies, robotic experiments, or image capture in crop fields.
- **Laboratory Environments:** Hormone analysis and some image data collection involve laboratory settings for specialized analyses.
- **Client-Specific Locations:** Data is collected at the client's premises or with their equipment, depending on their specific requirements.

Frequency and Context:

- **Real-time Automated Collection:** Data processed and saved during operation
- **Specific Agricultural Sampling:** E.g., Milk samples are taken daily or at intervals to monitor changes in progesterone levels in cows
- **Imagery Collection:** Handheld cameras or UAVs are used to capture images of soil and weeding activities.
- **Robotic & GPS Logging:** Data collection is geo-referenced through GPS modules mounted on the data collection platforms.
- **Laboratory Methods:** Encompass systematic techniques used in controlled settings to conduct scientific experiments and analyses, ensuring precision, standardized practices, and reliable results.
- **Context-Dependent Collection:** Data collection methods may be very specific on the context and specific requirements of the service.

3.3. Common terms in data quality assessment

Data quality assessment:

- **Sensor Technology and Calibration:** Regular calibration, and maintenance to ensure high-quality data collection
- **Visual Inspection and Image Analysis:** assessing image quality and labeling (automated or manual)
- **Hashing and Similarity Metrics:** image hashes to guarantee image uniqueness or finding similarities in images for refining datasets.
- **Label Verification and Detection:** Tools like Voxel51 detect labeling mistakes by evaluating model predictions against ground truth labels, enabling re-evaluation of labeled data.
- **Sample Hardness Assessment:** Utilizing neural network predictions, confidence levels, and entropy to determine sample hardness, aiding in selecting new samples for annotation.
- **Statistical Methods and Outlier Detection:** Using statistical methods to identify and remove outliers, ensuring data integrity.
- **System Maintenance and Repeatability:** Emphasis on repeatable testing, recording dataset states, and periodic health checks to maintain consistency and integrity.

- **Domain-Specific Data Assessment:** E.g., For spectral datasets, reflection spectra analysis, investigation of anomalies, and verification through capitation software are utilized.

AI model quality assessment:

- **Performance Metrics:** Standard metrics for evaluating AI model performance, including accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score for classification, mean IoU, frequency weighted IoU, pixel accuracy for segmentation, and Average Precision (AP), and mean Average Precision (mAP) for object detection or semantic segmentation.
- **Cross-Validation Techniques:** K-fold cross-validation is widely used to validate and assess model performance on various subsets of data, ensuring robustness.
- **Pre-Annotation Tools:** AI algorithms are used as pre-annotation tools to assist human annotators in tasks like bounding box generation or image pre-cutting. Human annotators correct AI-generated outputs to ensure annotation quality.
- **Manual Quality Assurance:** Annotators manually verify and correct outputs from pre-annotation tools to ensure accuracy and quality in the annotation process.
- **Carbon Footprint and Processing Efficiency:** Emphasis on evaluating models based on their processing time, cost, and their ability to work on edge devices while minimizing carbon footprint.
- **Baseline and Comparative Analysis:** Comparing AI models against state-of-the-art baselines for similar tasks to gauge performance and relevance.

Standardized Quality Labels for Data:

- **ISO Standards:**
 - o **ISO/IEC 25012:** This provides a comprehensive model for data quality, covering accuracy, completeness, consistency, credibility, currentness, and other dimensions.
 - o **ISO 8000:** Specifies requirements for data quality, encompassing provenance and process control for capturing data.
 - o **ISO 14040:** In contexts such as machine safety and life cycle assessment
- **Client-Specific Standards:** In some cases, adherence to specific standards is contingent upon client needs.
- **Framework and Guideline References:** References to ethical frameworks like the EU HLEG guidelines for responsible AI in the context of ELSA scan.

The comprehensive explanation of data types, collection locations, frequency and context within data collection practices, as well as the delineation of data quality assessment methods and standardised data quality labels, represent a crucial step towards establishing robust data management and evaluation frameworks within the scope of the project. These consolidated efforts underscore the commitment to promoting uniformity, consistency and integrity in the handling of data in various facets of the services, thereby setting the stage for future operational and collaborative progress.

4. Metadata Analysis

The primary goal of the metadata analysis in Section 4 is to comprehensively understand how metadata is currently being utilized within the AgrifoodTEF ecosystem. This involves examining the types of metadata that are most prevalent, the tools and platforms used for managing this metadata, and the standards applied to ensure consistency and quality across various services. By analyzing the responses from the Service Data Management Plan (sDMP) surveys, we aim to identify common practices, pinpoint areas for improvement, and understand the overall landscape of metadata usage within the project. This analysis is indispensable in guiding the development of more efficient and standardized metadata practices, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness and interoperability of services within AgrifoodTEF."

To conduct the metadata analysis, a graph database and a Large Language Model (LLM) were employed to process six key questions from the Service Data Management Plan (sDMP) responses of metadata. The responses yielded common terms related to metadata, which were then categorized under node labels such as "Metadata Type," "Tools and Platforms," "Metadata Standard," and "Succession on previous European projects." These terms, along with the frequency of their occurrence, are detailed in Annex 2.

The collected common terms were organized in a graph database (Neo4j). Each sDMP was linked to its associated common terms, enabling the graph database to manage relationships and connections between data entities within the survey responses. This systematic organization is depicted in Figure 1. A total of 50 sDMPs were analyzed.

To further analyze the data, the Louvain algorithm was utilized. This algorithm identifies clusters within the data, based on criteria such as metadata type, tool platforms, and metadata standards. This clustering provided deeper insights into the patterns and relationships inherent in the metadata usage across the AgrifoodTEF project.

The Louvain algorithm determined the following clusters in the graph database.

1. The largest cluster identified encompasses responses where no answer was given to the question, a significant observation in the survey. The prevalence of unanswered questions points to a clear trend. One possible reason for this could be that certain questions were not applicable to the specific service being addressed. However, the primary reason appears to be a lack of information or early stage of development of the services.
2. The second largest cluster relates to time stamps as a metadata type and the use of a folder structure to organize the data and metadata. This suggests that timestamps are an important metadata type and folder structures are most often used to store metadata that comprehends timestamps.
3. Other clusters relate to using specific tools with data or metadata types. For example, when the data comprehends the image format, a folder structure is often used to organize the data.

Figure 1: Graph data modelling - Blue Nodes: “sDMP”, Green Nodes: “Metadata Type”, Orange Nodes: “Tools and Platforms”, Purple Nodes: “Metadata Standard”.

The LLM (GPT3) was grounded on the composed graph database and was used to create a Neo4j query to question the database. The following questions were asked:

1. Which metadata types were used most, and how many respondents use them?

The five Metadata Types used most frequently are time stamp, not answered, location, weather, and system/sensor description.

- **Time Stamp:** As a crucial chronological reference for data points or images.
- **Location:** In image datasets, to denote the geographic origin of the data.
- **Weather Conditions:** In agricultural or environmental studies, to provide context regarding weather during data collection.
- **Sensor Information:** Associated with image datasets, detailing sensor characteristics and configurations.

2. Which tool platforms were used most and how many respondents use them?

The five Tool Platforms used most by the respondents are folder structure, not answered, FMS, PostgreSQL, and InfluxDB.

- **PostgreSQL and InfluxDB:** Used as a database management system to store and manage metadata. Postgres, with its PostGIS plugin, for its spatial data capabilities. InfluxDB is used for time-series data storage.
- **Folder Structure:** Often utilized as a basic method for organizing and managing data and metadata. Shared folder structures are a common approach for storing data and associated metadata.
- **Farm Management Software (FMS):** Mentioned as a platform for storing crop management data, likely used for organizing agricultural-related metadata.

3. Which metadata standards were used most, and how many respondents use them?

The 5 standards metadata that was used most are not answered, coco forma, Pascal VOC, Yes, undefined, and Json.

- **COCO Format:** Standard dataset format for object detection tasks in computer vision.
- **Pascal VOC:** Dataset format for object detection and classification tasks.
- **JSON:** Lightweight data interchange format using key-value pairs.
- **YOLO Format:** A data structure for YOLO's real-time object detection.
- **Labelbox:** Platform for annotating data for machine learning tasks.
- **RDF:** Standard model for describing web resources in a graph format.

4. Which tools platforms were used most in combination with the metadata type 'time stamp'?

The tool platform used most in combination with the metadata type 'time stamp' is folder structure.

5. Which tool platforms and metadata types were mostly combined, give the top 5?

1. 'Folder structure' and 'time stamp' (18 occurrences)
2. 'Folder structure' and 'location' (10 occurrences)
3. 'Folder structure' and 'weather' (9 occurrences)
4. 'Folder structure' and 'acquisition software' (7 occurrences)
5. No information was provided for the fifth combination

6. What is the strongest association between a metadata type and a tool platform?

The folder structure is the strongest association between a metadata type and a tool platform. It was used in 18 instances, making it the most commonly combined combination.

The Graph Database and the Language Model synergy provided a more holistic view of the survey dataset. The most important metadata for the services provided appears to be the timestamp, location, and weather conditions. In question 5 of the graph database, most of this metadata appears to be stored in a folder structure. The answer to question 6 also states a strong association between the metadata and folder structure. 35% of the sDMP's mentioned 'Folder structure' as a tool or platform to maintain the data and metadata organization, and 23% were unanswered. Maintaining a folder structure for data storage is approachable and only needs a few skills. Folder structures are a viable choice for the storage of large data objects. However, they cannot enforce data consistency and integrity to maintain metadata and increase the risks of errors or inconsistent duplicates in the collected metadata. Database technologies (relational, time-series, document-based, graph, ...) or higher lever Farm Management Systems (FMS) overcome these issues. Also, other tools mentioned (Excell, R/python) can incorporate data sanity checks, though this has to be carefully implemented.

Metadata standards mentioned for AI-related metadata are COCO, Yolo, and Pascal VOC. It is important to note that ISO standards or standards from international standardization organizations were only mentioned once during the data management of the services.

Many of the nodes participated in the European Demeter and IOF2020 projects. Diverse Engagement with Prior Projects: Services exhibit various approaches in leveraging the outcomes or findings of previous European projects. Some actively engage, while others consider or apply relevant findings aligning with their domain or needs.

Data Sharing and Data Protection (data storage, backup, accessibility, and ethical guidelines) are often performed in collaboration between the researchers and the IT department. Terminology, like the FAIR Data principles, is only mentioned once in all the surveys.

5. Ontology for metadata standards

In this section, we look into the development and significance of an ontology for metadata standards within the AgrifoodTEF project. An ontology is a structured and systematic framework designed to categorize and interrelate various metadata terms and standards. This framework is key for creating a coherent and unified approach to handling metadata across the diverse range of services and initiatives within AgrifoodTEF. The development of this ontology is not just a technical exercise, but it represents a critical step towards enhancing data interoperability, facilitating clearer communication, and streamlining data management processes within our project. Through this ontology, we aim to establish a common language and a shared understanding of metadata practices, essential for the success and advancement of the AgrifoodTEF project.

5.1. Established ontology for the metadata:

The following ontologies were described in the sDMPs and are already implemented in some of the services:

- **NGSI for Storing Metadata** (<https://www.nsgi.nl/>)
- **Agrovoc** (<https://agrovoc.fao.org/browse/agrovoc/en/>)
- **Zenodo Metadata Reference Standard** (<https://zenodo.org/>)
- **EDI Standards** (<https://www.ibm.com/docs/en/b2bis?topic=basics-edi-standards>)
- **Semantics and Working Groups:** Refers to semantic models like *drmAgro*, often detailed in research papers or defined within working groups for metadata organization and standardization.
- **Research Domain-Specific Ontologies:** Utilizes terminology specific to the research domain for metadata structuring and categorization.

5.2. Maintaining ontology

Adopting a common ontology improves agricultural data's understandability, usability, and interoperability. By providing a structured and standardized representation of the agricultural domain, ontologies facilitate data sharing with the clients and among the AgrifoodTEF nodes and satellites. Therefore, the applied ontology should be easy to consult by all users. This section highlights the various methodologies and practices employed within the AgrifoodTEF project to keep the ontology aligned with the latest agricultural terms, research findings, and data management trends. The applied ontology should continuously reflect the current state of knowledge and practice in the field related to the service.

Below, we summarise key practices in the sDMPs that explain used strategies for documenting ontology. This comprehensive set of practices serves as a basis for improved data understanding and uniformity contributing significantly to the effectiveness of data management within the AgrifoodTEF project.

- **Attribute Naming and Common Agricultural Terms:** Uses attribute naming based on common agricultural terms to facilitate understanding.
- **Ontology Alignment with Research Papers:** Aligns ontology structure according to research papers, ensuring consistency with the scientific literature.

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- **Documentation:** Provides comprehensive explanations, protocols, variable descriptions, and definitions in documentation to facilitate understanding.
 - **Client-Provided Descriptions:** Descriptions and hypotheses ensure a clear understanding of the metadata used.
 - **Explanatory Vocabulary List and Goal/Scope:** An explanatory vocabulary list and a table detailing goal and scope, aiding understanding of metadata related to Life Cycle Assessment.
 - **GitLab Documentation:** Documents datasets on a GitLab page, with descriptions for improved comprehension.
 - **Unique Identifiers and Standardized Descriptions:** Uses unique identifiers assigned by Zenodo and standardized data descriptions to ensure clarity and understanding.
 - **Semantic Model Definitions:** Definitions within semantic models are provided, contributing to a clearer understanding of the ontology.

Our Service Data Management Plan (sDMP) survey has highlighted a need for a comprehensive ontology within the AgrifoodTEF project and the knowledge exchange of specialized data management tools. This marks a crucial step towards implementing effective ontologies, aimed at enhancing data coherence and interoperability across our services. However, it's important to acknowledge that we are at the early stages of this initiative. Many of our services are still in the process of being fully developed, which presents both challenges and opportunities in integrating and evolving our ontological frameworks. As AgrifoodTEF continues to grow and mature, our commitment to refining and adapting these ontologies will be indispensable in ensuring they meet the evolving needs of our project and stakeholders.

6. Data sharing and protection

Establishing robust data storage and sharing protocols and implementing responsible data management practices to safeguard valuable data is crucial. Analysis of sDMPs reveals many practices that contribute significantly to effective data protection. These practices, described below, provide a comprehensive framework for securing data and ensuring its integrity throughout the research lifecycle.

6.1. Data storage and data backup:

- **Server, desktop, and backup:** Indicates storage on servers and local storage on desktops, involving regular backups and copies for data safety.
- **Open Data Repositories:** On platforms like GitHub, Gitlab and Zenodo, code and data are stored and version-controlled on password-protected servers
- **MS Teams/SharePoint with Daily Backups:** Relies on Microsoft Teams and SharePoint platforms for data storage and conducts daily backups for data security.

6.2. Methods used for data sharing:

- **Sharing through Website Interface and local Servers:** including requesting data access via the specific website interfaces. And servers with authentication, internally hosted.
- **Data Shared on Network Drives and Repositories:** Results, point spectra, and object-level spectra are shared on network drives, SharePoint, Gitlab, GitHub and Zenodo.

6.3. Responsible for data management:

A dedicated team of professionals oversees data management. The **IT department** plays a central role in data infrastructure and security, while **researchers** are responsible for data creation and processing. The **Data Compliance team/officer** ensures compliance with data privacy and protection regulations, while the **AI Testing department** maintains the integrity of data used in AI models. This collaborative approach ensures comprehensive data management and compliance.

In conclusion, the fundamental importance of robust data sharing and protection within the AgrifoodTEF project cannot be overstated. The insights gained from our Service Data Management Plans (sDMPs) represent only an initial survey and a preliminary attempt to collect comprehensive information on these practices. Despite being in the early stages, our findings reveal a range of effective methods contributing significantly to data security and integrity. From thorough data storage and backup protocols to secure data sharing methods and responsible data management, these practices form a foundational framework for further deployment of data security approach in our project. This comprehensive approach not only ensures the safeguarding of valuable research data but also promotes accessibility and compliance with regulatory standards. As the AgrifoodTEF project progresses, we anticipate further refinement and enhancement of these data sharing and protection strategies, continuing to support the integrity and success of our testing and experimentation initiative in the agrifood technology sector.

7. Working groups

In this section the formation and function of specialized working groups within the AgrifoodTEF project, established in November 2023 is explained within Work Package 4 (WP4). The Working groups serve as a collaborative tool, fostering discussions and information exchange among partners operating at a service level. These groups are formed specifically when multiple partners offer analogous services, aiming to collectively identify and define the fundamental building blocks of these services along with the correlated standards. The working groups are using the preparatory work on common terms, ontologies and meta data standards as a steppingstone towards the common language that needs to be developed in the agrifoodTEF project. These working groups will play a crucial role in coordinating related standards relevant to the development of new services and ensure alignment with standardization needs arising from Task 4.2. The formation of these various working groups (WGs) is a necessary step in fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange among the service level partners of the AgrifoodTEF project and serve as instrumental forums for maintaining industry standards and best practices. Their core responsibilities include identifying, assessing and integrating relevant industry standards and common metadata into new services, while simultaneously studying existing standards to identify areas in need of improvement or potential gaps and promote the development of ontologies. This holistic approach ensures consistent services, interoperability and compliance with quality standards.

Simultaneously, the focus of these working groups will also be on the identification of shared and distinctive testing and experimentation methods (essential components of services) which fits seamlessly with the close relationship between common terms and metadata standards. Moreover, the delineation of working groups aligns with different facets within the AI and robotics ecosystem in the agri-food sector, ensuring comprehensive coverage that is absolutely necessary for the AgrifoodTEF project.

The formation and focus of each working group were carefully determined through collaborative discussions with partners involved in WP4. To guide this process, these partners developed a strategic matrix that intersected technical competencies, such as AI and standards, with domain expertise, including areas like precision livestock farming. This matrix served as a tool to align the needs of the project with the available expertise, ensuring that each working group was both relevant and well supported.

Subsequently, all partners in the AgrifoodTEF project were invited to assign their experts to various domains within this matrix. The initial list of working groups was then created based on the domains that attracted the most expertise. This approach ensured that the working groups were not only aligned with the project's technical and domain-specific needs but also adequately staffed with professionals who could drive significant progress in each area.

As a result, the working groups represent a well-balanced blend of technical and domain-specific insights, fitted to address the complex challenges and opportunities within the AgrifoodTEF project.

The working groups have only just started their monthly meeting but the results that will be generated by these working groups will potentially offer several service-level benefits:

- Improved interoperability: The adoption of uniform terms and standards promotes seamless data exchange between different systems and applications, potentially improving efficiency and productivity.
- Improved data quality: Standardized terminologies and standards contribute to the accuracy and consistency of data, thereby increasing the quality of analyses and decision-making processes.
- Simplifying collaboration: Common terms and standards facilitate project collaboration and data sharing among stakeholders, which can promote innovation and effective problem solving.

WG	Name	Topics	Lead
1	Robotics	Robotics (incl. UAV & implements)	(FR) & Marijke H. (BE)
2	Sensor testing	Sensor testing (vision, hyperspectral, audio, other)	Peter R.-N. (AT)
3	Safety tests	Safety tests (obstacle detection, follow-me function, ARPA tests, geofencing)	Julien P. (FR)
4	AI pipeline and model testing	AI pipeline and model testing (performance, robustness, explain ability)	Raphael F. (IT)
5	ELSA, LCA, BM and Usability	ELSA (ethical, legal and social aspects), conformity to policy and LCA, Business modeling and Usability & UX testing (UAT)	Mireille v. H. (NL)
6	Data	data infrastructure and handling (provision of data, interoperability), data analytics and visualization, meta-data standards, synthetic data	Raul P. (PL)
7	Simulation and testing in a digital environment	Simulation and testing in a digital environment	Fredrik B. (SE)
8	Livestock	Livestock	Magdalena W. (AT)

Table 1: Initial Set of Working Groups for agrifoodTEF project

The establishment and strategic formation of these working groups within the AgrifoodTEF project represent an indispensable next step in transforming the outcomes of our Service Data Management Plans (sDMPs) into practical measures. This is for achieving a common language in the AgrifoodTEF project.

8. Discussion, Conclusion and Next Steps

Establishing a common language within the AgrifoodTEF project, including standardized formats for data labels and a standardized ontology of terms, is an extremely challenging task, particularly when the project is in its infancy and nearly all services are under development. This task not only requires strong coordination and mutual understanding between the partners but also a very dynamic approach to adapt to evolving needs and insights during the early stages of the AgrifoodTEF project. This task set out to make an initial list of common terms and metadata standards and this is only the starting point of a long endeavor towards this AgrifoodTEF common.

The introduction of the Service Data Management Plans (sDMPs) played a crucial role in the AgrifoodTEF project, marking the beginning of a collective effort towards a unified language and framework. By engaging all partners in completing this extensive survey, we initiated a process of active reflection and analysis across the consortium. This exercise compelled each partner to thoroughly examine their current practices and to think more critically about the design and structure of their services. It was a start point that challenged our partners to conceptualize and articulate their data management approaches more coherently. This introspective analysis laid the basis for developing a common language and set of standards within the AgrifoodTEF ecosystem, fostering a shared understanding and vision, essential for the collaborative success of AgrifoodTEF.

Via the sDMPs we got a view on common terms used within the project and the results show the necessity of a unified terminology framework across various services. The explanation of various aspects of data collection practices, including data types, collection locations, frequency and context, along with the detailed mapping of data quality assessment methods and standardised data quality labels, is a first step for all partners towards a robust data management for their services. As we move forward, these findings set the stage for more efforts in harmonizing terminology within the AgrifoodTEF project. Implementing these common terms is now a first and necessary step. The inclusion of client-specific standards and alignment with internationally recognized frameworks will be prioritized to ensure comprehensive and ethical data processing practices.

The observation in the survey, where numerous questions remained unanswered, warrants attention. The lack of responses could be attributed to various factors, but the most prevalent reason appears to be the limited knowledge of the responders, or the early developmental stage of the services. The readiness level of the services plays a significant role in the ability to provide comprehensive metadata information. This finding highlights an area within the AgrifoodTEF project that may require further development and understanding to enhance the overall effectiveness of our metadata strategies as we strive towards establishing a common language within the AgrifoodTEF ecosystem.

The metadata analysis reveals significant insights into the current state of data management within the AgrifoodTEF services. A key observation is the prevalent use of folder structures for organizing metadata, indicating a preference for traditional, hierarchical data storage methods. This widespread use of folder structures, particularly in conjunction with metadata types like timestamps, suggests a foundational approach to data organization that prioritizes ease of access and user-friendliness. However, it may also indicate a lack of knowledge of data management systems that are much more capable of maintaining consistency and integrity of the data. The analysis highlights the importance of timestamps as a metadata type underscores their crucial role in providing chronological context to data, an essential aspect in the agricultural sector. Similarly, the importance of geographical context is indicated by the frequent citation of location metadata highlights.

Weather conditions as a metadata type underscore the importance of environmental factors in agrifood experiments. Indeed, recording external conditions is crucial, as they can significantly affect agricultural processes and outcomes. This underlines the need for robust metadata practices that can capture and convey such critical contextual information.

Metadata standards mentioned for AI-related metadata are COCO, Yolo, and Pascal VOC. It is important to say that ISO standards or standards from international standardization organizations were only mentioned once within the data management of the services.

While many of our partners are deeply engaged in the ecosystem of digital agrifood, with participation in projects like Demeter, IOF2020, and Smart AgriHubs, this engagement has not yet translated into a strong integration of terminology, linked to the FAIR Data principles. These principles are mentioned rarely in all the surveys

The Service Data Management Plan (sDMP) survey highlighted the need for a comprehensive ontology within AgrifoodTEF, marking a step towards efficient ontologies aimed at improving data consistency and interoperability across our services. The focus should be on continuously improving and updating these ontology frameworks as our services develop and mature within AgrifoodTEF.

The importance of robust mechanisms for sharing and protecting data in the AgrifoodTEF services is another clear outcome of our survey. A proactive attitude in developing these strategies will be crucial to maintaining the integrity and success of our agrifood technology initiatives.

Overall, the Service Data Management Plan Survey within the AgrifoodTEF service portfolio has provided important insights into common terminology, metadata standards, data collection practices, quality assessments, and collaborative frameworks across TEF nodes and satellites. While there is a lot of work in implementing consistent, interoperable data management practices, it's essential to balance these efforts. Excessive emphasis on standardization may hinder the final project goal of deploying qualitative services. Data management is essential, yet it must always serve as a means to an end, facilitating improved services for our clients. This is where our working groups play an important role. Their task is to exchange information on existing data ontologies and management tools across various technical domains of AgrifoodTEF, such as robotics, sensor testing, and AI pipelines, to ensure service quality. These groups are key in ensuring that each step towards standardization and a common language is focused on enhancing service delivery. The initial list of common terms and metadata standards described here is a starting point to tackle that challenge.

Annex 1

GENERAL	
Service	
Service ID	
sDMP version	
DATA COLLECTION What data do you collect?	
Data type(s)	E.g., Data type of raw data and/or accompanying data labels
Where and how is the data collected?	Provide a short description to create context where and how the data is collected/created.
Data formats (extension)	E.g., 2D images (png/tiff/raw/...), 3D images (ply/pcd/...), Orthophoto (tiff), Multispectral images, Textual data (csv/txt/docx/excel/...) Binary data (pkl/mat/...)
DATA QUALITY AND DATA USE For what purpose will you use this data?	
How do you assess the quality of your data?	E.g., Data inconsistency (wrong match in labels, raw data, metadata), redundancy E.g., Correctness of data labels
Is this dataset also relevant for other services? If yes, list the other applicable catalogue services.	Provide the service names and IDs
If you use AI models in your service, how do you assess the quality of your AI models?	E.g., Benchmarking against well-established datasets, E.g., For unsupervised models metrics like silhouette score or Davies-Bouldin index, E.g., K-fold cross-validation
Do you use any standardized quality labels for data that you use in your service? If yes, please provide examples and relevant sources.	E.g., ISO 8000, the FAIR Data Principles
METADATA: What descriptive information about the data you collect?	
Metadata types	E.g., Time Stamp, location, calibration files, weather conditions, ...
What tools or platforms are used to manage this metadata?	E.g., Postgres, postgis, folder structure, ...
What metadata are you currently collecting that extends the scope of this service and could be beneficial for future services?	E.g., Next to the position also the orientation of an image is registered, information that is currently not used in the developed service.
Is recording metadata obligatory for your service?	Is the dataset still useful for this service when the metadata is lost?

METADATA STANDARDS:

Do you use any specific metadata standards when recording, storing, or sharing your service data?

How is the ontology for this metadata established?	E.g., research domain related ontology. Ontology used in your organisation.
How will you ensure that others are able to understand the ontology used in your metadata description?	E.g., Documentation, attribute naming, ...
Are you aware of any standards/examples that could relate to your metadata?	E.g., Metadata standards: Dublin Core, FGDC (Federal Geographic Data Committee standard), ISO 19115 (for geographic information), AgMES (Agricultural Metadata Element Set) E.g., Data label standards: YOLO format, COCO format, ...
Are you building on the results of any previous European project?	E.g., IOF2020, Demeter or Atlas?

DATA SHARING AND PROTECTION

How do guarantee data availability and protection?

How is the data storage and data backup done?	E.g., Zenodo, a general-purpose open-access repository or E.g., Labels, model weights and database are backup-ed daily within the satellite's network infrastructure
How is data sharing done?	E.g., REST-API to provide the data E.g., Djust-connect for the legal aspect of data sharing

Annex 2

Metadata Types		Tools and Platforms		Metadata Standards		Succession on previous European project	
time stamp	27	folder structure	27	not answered	34	not answered	39
not answered	15	not answered	18	Coco format	7	demeter	5
location	12	fms	4	pascal voc	5	iof2020	4
weather	10	software infrastructure	2	yes	5	open-access data	2
test scenario	7	postgresql	4	json	3	atlas	2
system/sensor description	7	influxdb	2	yolo format	2	agrobofood	1
acquisition software	7	relational database	2	labelbox	1	data from european project	1
calibration files	6	ms forms	2	rdf	1	cybele	1
agronomic	4	excel	2	dublin core	1	spectrofood	1
unique identifier	3	r/python	2	own label formats	1	smartagrihubs	1
dns server	2	capture software	1	roboflow	1	stembot	1
dimension	2	file properties and details	1	v7labs	1	wikileaks	1
unit	2	insertmaaltijd application	1	fair data principles	1	flaxsense	1
variety	2	data provider	1	Labelstud	1	cimat	1
crop	2	internal protocols	1	txt	1		
sensor settings	2	microsoft office	1	environmental footprint methodology	1		
soil conditions	2	weather station	1				
hyperparameters	1	readme.txt	1				
origin	1	voxel51	1				
excel	1	protocol	1				
csv	1	barcode	1				
docx	1						
date	1						
meal type	1						
meal composition	1						
nutrition values	1						
recording date	1						
camera type	1						
camera setting	1						
orientation	1						

hitch and implement states	1					
gps accuracy	1					
country	1					
facility	1					
robot	1					
specific sensor model	1					
crop species	1					
weed species	1					
camera intrinsics	1					
sensor configuration parameters	1					
total duration	1					
number of frames per data type	1					
raw image resolution	1					
angle of image acquisition	1					
protocols	1					
record of hardware metrics	1					
ground humidity	1					
dataset version	1					
weather conditions	1					
vineyard density	1					
model version	1					
spraying device	1					
sensor width and height	1					
dimensions	1					
resolution	1					
color depth	1					
format	1					
light level	1					
camera position	1					
logs	1					
image	1					
video metadata	1					
focal distance	1					
system description	1					
sensor description	1					
compass heading	1					
altitude reading	1					
latitude management	1					

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crop	1						
longitude	1						
pressure values	1						
crop management data	1						

